

Estimation of wealth index in Brazil

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BELMONT FORUM

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We acknowledge the Traditional Owners and Custodians of the land and sea in all nations. We honour their profound connections to land, water, biodiversity and culture and pay our respects to their Elders past, present and emerging.

Motivation

- Socioeconomic indicators are useful for **decision making**. However, can be expensive, difficult to obtain, and time consuming.
- **Census** surveys are collected every **10 years**, which may not reflect reality in ‘real time’.
 - Due to pandemics, next survey will be available in 2022? Last one is 2010.
- Alternatively, cell phone usage data, **remote sensing imagery**, aerial imagery can be widely, **low-cost**, and **easily accessible**.

Objective

Infer well-being indicators from satellite images (multispectral Landsat and nightlight) images by using **transfer learning** of a trained model on Africa's countries **to the Brazilian territory**, more specifically on **Vale do Ribeira**.

Material & Methods

Area of study

- Vale do Ribeira

DL model trained on Africa's countries

Satellite imagery

- Multispectral (diurn)
- Nightlight

Material & Methods

Area of study

- Vale do Ribeira

Vale do Ribeira

Vale do Ribeira

- **28,306 km²** spread across **São Paulo and Paraná**
- 30 municipalities
- 954 census tracts
 - 880 are valid census tracts due to data privacy issues.
- **Largest contiguous area of protected Atlantic Forest** in Brazil.
 - Declared a **Natural Heritage** in 1999,.
 - Represents 21% of the remaining forest in the country.

Surrounded by many Protected Areas

- **62%** corresponds to PAs.

Surrounded by many Protected Areas

- **62%** corresponds to PAs.
- Although has **high economic development**, it is considered **economically poor** and has the **lowest Human Development Index (HDI)** in the state of São Paulo.

Urban/Rural distribution

Material & Methods

DL model trained on
Africa's countries

DL model trained on Africa's countries

- Period: **1996-2019**
- DHS data: **36182** villages (24 countries)
- “Wealth index” calculated using PCA from **93 DHS surveys**
 - Variables such as: number of **rooms**, **electricity**, quality of **house floors**, **water supply** and **toilet**, **phone**, **radio**, **tv**, **car** and **motorbike**.

DL model trained on Africa's countries

Model trained with high performance $R^2 = 0.691$

Material & Methods

Satellite imagery

- Multispectral (diurn)
- Nightlight

Satellite image acquisition for 2010, 2015, 2020

GOOGLE EARTH
ENGINE

Nightlight (NL)imagery

Resolution < 1 km/pixel (927.67 m)

Source: DMSP OLS: Global Radiance-Calibrated Nighttime
Lights Version 4, Defense Meteorological Program
Operational Linescan System (NL).

Daytime Multispectral Landsat
(MS) imagery

Resolution 30m/pixel.

Source: USGS Landsat 5/7 Surface Reflectance Tier 1 (MS).
Bands RED, GREEN, BLUE, NIR (Near Infrared), SWIR1,
SWIR2, and TEMP1.

Results

Estimated Wealth index 2010

High WI corresponds to urban tracts

Urban/Rural distribution

Validation of the transfer learning

Pearson correlation between ground truth **HDI-income** and **estimated Wealth Index** from **2010**

	HDI Income
r^2	0.51

Estimated WI evolution

2010

2015

2020

1.14 0.84 0.54 0.24 -0.06 -0.36 -0.66

“wealth index” tends to evolve slowly over time

Estimated WI for census tracts samples

Wealth index trend from 2010, 2015, 2020

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSION

Potential

- Remote sensing imagery and Deep Learning are low resource consumption and the wide availability.
- Collected more frequently rather than census surveys (10 years).

Next steps

- Investigate the socioeconomic impact of the estimated Wealth index
- Investigate the effects of Protected Area to the well-being of near municipalities.

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